

The Impact of Non- Intellectual Factors on Students' Educational Performance of Rajkot City

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Abstract

The aim of study is to determine the impact of non- intellectual factors on students' educational performance of Rajkot city. They are identifying as learning, habits, motivation and attitude. This study also aims to identify whether the said elements are impacted or not. The multiple regression is used to examine the results.

Key words: impact, educational performance, students, learning habits, motivation, attitude, emotions.

1 Introduction:

With the rapid changes in time and era, students feel the wave of globalization. Oneself also affected by the intellectual and non- intellectual factors in the focus of study. The purpose of study is to determine the impact of non- intellectual factors on students' educational performance. The study carries out the following factors- learning habits, attitude, emotions and motivation of students.

2. Review of literature:

Goleman in year 1995, considered the emotions are considered as the basic need of students for development, while Mr. Reuven ability of individual and adoption also affected by the non- intellectual factors sometimes.

Prof. Howard, found that non- intellectual factors are developed by individual is by own self and adopted by the nearest environment by the personnel. Mayer in year 1993 defines the non- intellectual factor as psychological state of individual. In year 2008, again Mayer stated by research that, individual have also sophisticated processing of emotions by the factors.

3. Research Methodology:

Research Problem:

“The impact of non- intellectual factors on students’ educational performance of Rajkot city”

Objectives of Study:

Impact of non- intellectual factors like learning, attitude, emotions and motivation affects the students’ educational performance.

Hypothesis of Study:

Null Hypothesis:

- H0: There is no significant correlation between learning habits of students and educational performance of Rajkot city.
- H0: There is no significant correlation between attitude of students and educational performance of Rajkot city.
- H0: There is no significant correlation between emotions of students and educational performance of Rajkot city.
- H0: There is no significant correlation between motivation of students and educational performance of Rajkot city.

Alternative Hypothesis:

- H1: There is a significant correlation between learning habits of students and educational performance of Rajkot city.
- H1 : There is a significant correlation between attitude of students and educational performance of Rajkot city.
- H1: There is a significant correlation between emotions of students and educational performance of Rajkot city.
- H1: There is a significant correlation between motivation of students and educational performance of Rajkot city.

Population of Study and Sample Size:

The population of the study includes 100 students of secondary school to Post Graduate level students of Rajkot city. (Gujarat State)

Tools & Techniques of Study:

Data has been collected through the primary source with help convince sampling method, using structural questionnaire. For best output of result, multiple regression is applied.

Data is computed by using Microsoft Excel 2007 and SPSS software.

4. Data Analysis & Interpretations:

Data were analyzed by the multiple regression with help of SPSS software.

Variable	Multiple R	β	Standard Error β	Beta	t	Significant of t	Result of Hypothesis
Learning Habits	0.58	0.584	0.040	0.59	14.35	0.000	H1 Accepted
Attitude	0.23	0.54	0.130	0.263	4.058	0.000	H1 Accepted
Emotions	0.29	-0.37	0.128	-0.183	-2.918	0.003	H1 Accepted
Motivation	0.26	0.46	0.153	0.165	3.121	0.004	H1 Accepted

As result, the significant value is less than 0.05 so H₀ is rejected.

It is said that, non –intellectual factors are directly or indirectly impact on study and students' performances.

5. Findings & Conclusion of Study:

The non- intellectual factors in recent study based on 100 students, it is found that, these factors include...

- learning habit of individual,
- attitude either positive or negative towards the study,
- even emotions of students,
- plus motivation of person somehow impact on their performances towards the study.

Theses all factors are consider as non- intellectual factors but the effects on individuals is vast then the intellectual factors. Because, somehow these factors are by born or adopted from the nearest environment and now it considered as individual traits.

So, from the research work well said that, there is a significant correlation between learning habits, attitude, emotions even motivation of students which impact the educational performance of Rajkot city.

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